

A modified phase-field model for cohesive interface failure in quasi-brittle solids

Sijia Liu^a, Yunteng Wang^{b,*}, Wei Wu^b

^a School of Civil Engineering, Qingdao University of Technology, Qingdao, 266033, China

^b Institut für Geotechnik, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien, Feistmantelstraße 4, 1180 Wien, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Phase-field
Cohesive interface
Traction–separation
Damage law
Degradation function
Crack-interface interaction

ABSTRACT

We formulate a modified phase-field model for cohesive interface failure in quasi-brittle solids. Our model has two novel features: (i) a traction–separation–damage law for damage process; (ii) an energetic degradation function controlled by critical gap ratio. This modification offers an attractive approach to simulate the cohesive interface failure process. We also provide a robust numerical solution strategy to treat the spatio-temporal evolution of cohesive interface failure. Our model is validated by two benchmark problems including the constant strain patch test and mode-I delamination test. The numerical simulations are compared with some published data. We proceed to apply this model to study the complex failure mechanism of a peeling test on bi-material plates and crack impinging on interfaces in different scenarios, where the effects of critical gap ratios and interface inclination angles are discussed.

1. Introduction

The presence of interfaces, as weak or strong layers, plays a crucial role in the mechanical responses and failure characteristics of different engineering materials, such as composites [1–3], geological media [4], and concretes [5]. Some previous effort has contributed to improve the performance of interface adhesion in multi-material composite components and structures, which are beneficial for joint strength and bond toughness [6,7]. However, the basal shear-zone interfaces between sliding masses and bedrocks may trigger the occurrence of catastrophic landslides [8–10]. The complex interfacial solid stems from the evolution, interaction and competition among interfaces, bulk cracks and bulk matrix, which significantly affect the mechanical responses of these systems, such as matrix/fiber debonding [11], hydraulic fractures impinging on natural interfaces [12], and intergranular/transgranular fracture in heterogeneous microstructures [13].

Over the last decades, the interface failure has been extensively studied by laboratory experiments [6,14,15] and theoretical analyses [16–18]. The laboratory tests reveal the mechanism of crack penetration and deflection in solids with interfaces, which still poses formidable challenge [19–21]. Williams [16] provided an analytical solution of the stress and strain states around interfaces in dissimilar media under symmetric and antisymmetric loading. Linear elastic fracture mechanics has been applied to study the interaction mechanism between cracks and interfaces, such as stationary/dynamic crack impinging on interfaces [22] and anisotropic interface failure [17]

in bi-material media [18]. However, the analytical and theoretical analyses have some inherent difficulties in capturing the full-field quantitative evolution, i.e., multiple crack deflection [23] and complex impinging problems [21].

Numerical simulation provides a full-field quantitative tool for high-fidelity modeling interface failure in quasi-brittle solids and better understanding of the hidden mechanism. Recently, some numerical approaches have been developed to simulate the interface failure and the interaction mechanism between cracks and interfaces [24–26]. In the framework of standard finite element method (FEM), the independent interfacial regions were adopted for analyzing the interfacial damage processes [27–30]. Some cohesive elements were used to simulate the fiber debonding and laminates delamination in composite structures [31,32]. However, some inherent deficits of the FEM particularly the mesh-alignment issue in limits its predictive capabilities of interface failure analysis. To overcome this issue, some enrichment strategies were proposed in standard FEM framework, such as extended finite element method (XFEM) [33–35] and phantom node method [36]. However, such numerical approaches require additional *ad-hoc* failure criteria to handle the some complex failure phenomena, e.g., crack branching [37], doubly deflection [38], and dynamic impinging [39].

Phase-field method is a regularized energy-based numerical approach with variational formulations to tackle discontinuous problems in solids by minimization of elastic and fracture energies [40,41]. Similar to the integral-type nonlocal theory, i.e., peridynamics [42–47], the

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: yunteng.wang@boku.ac.at (Y. Wang), wei.wu@boku.ac.at (W. Wu).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2023.108368>

Received 26 December 2022; Received in revised form 23 March 2023; Accepted 6 April 2023

Available online 14 April 2023

0020-7403/© 2023 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

phase-field approach has some distinct advantages over other numerical approaches in dealing with nucleation and propagation problems of discontinuities. In phase-field simulations, the sharp discontinuous topology is approximated as a diffuse damage zone by a scalar phase-field variable d and internal characteristic length scale ℓ , which not only interpolates between fully failed and intact states of solids, but also bridge the gap between microscopic and macroscopic properties of materials. Furthermore, phase-field approach allows the propagation of discontinuities without requiring some tracing technologies and *ad-hoc* criteria. Some specific failure criteria can be integrated into the phase-field framework [48], enabling simulations of complex failure phenomena. These distinct advantages have made the phase-field approach an ideal tool to address many discontinuous problems in solids, including quasi-brittle/brittle fracture [49–53], ductile fracture [54, 55], dynamic fracture [56,57], hydraulic fracture [58,59], and strain localization [60,61].

More recent works on phase-field modeling focused on dealing with interface failure problems. The computational strategies for interface failure in quasi-brittle/brittle materials can be classified into two categories: (i) hybrid approach coupled with cohesive zone model (CZM) [11,21,30,62–66], and (ii) the energy-based one for diffused interfaces [13,26,67–73]. On the one hand, the initial attempt by incorporating cohesive zone model (CZM) into the phase-field approach [74] is to address the cohesive fracture, where the dissipative mechanism is different from brittle fracture. The phase-field variable, as an auxiliary field, enables the incorporation of cohesive traction during crack opening. Inspired by this idea, Paggi and Reinoso [21] proposed a phase-field coupled CZM to study laminated composites, where phase-field model is employed to describe the brittle bulk fracture, while CZM is used to describe the interface debonding. Zhang et al. [75] combined a phase-field model and cohesive element for modeling progressive failure in composite materials. This hypothesis is suitable for both brittle and cohesive interface failure behaviors, which has been extended to solve other problems, such as layered composites [11,30,62,75–77] and poly-crystallines [63,78]. For example, Tarafder et al. [79] developed a unified phase field model for simulating finite deformation crack evolution and interfacial decohesion in multi-phase elastic materials. Bui and Hu reviewed the fundamentals of phase-field approach as well as the modeling strategies for laminates at multiple length scales [80]. Chen and de Borst contributed to a concise description of cohesive zone models and phase-field approximations of brittle fracture, and studied the convergence of phase-field model towards a cohesive zone model [81]. On the other hand, some regularization strategies for interfacial surface energy were proposed to represent the diffuse interfaces in phase-field framework [67–70,78,82–84]. Hansen-Dörr et al. [69] assigned the modified fracture toughness over a diffused length for interfaces based on the surface energy equivalence. Nguyen et al. [67,68] incorporated a level-set function to the high-order phase-field variables accounting for equivalent surface energy of diffuse interfaces. Yoshioka et al. [70] derived an effective interface fracture toughness based on the diffused length and fracture toughness for bulk matrix and interfaces in the phase-field framework.

In this work, we propose modified phase-field formulations for modeling cohesive interface failure in quasi-brittle solids. We introduce zero-thickness interface elements for representing interfaces, which are fully compatible with phase-field approach in the bulk region. The cohesive traction on these interface elements can be calculated based on the relative displacements and damage gradients within a consistent phase-field framework. This numerical strategy can also account for the interactions between bulk crack surfaces and interfaces without recourse to additional level-set functions and phase-field variable orders. To model cohesive interfacial damage process, we also propose a novel parameterized degradation function in our model instead of the classical CZM. The parameters of this novel degradation function can be obtained from the global mechanical responses. Compared with the reported hybrid phase-field CZM [21,30,75] and cohesive

phase-field models [79,81,85,86], our model has two novel features: (i) incorporation of interfacial damage process to form the traction–separation–damage law on zero-thickness interface elements; and (ii) bypassing the tension cut-off characteristics in the traditional CZM to avoid numerical oscillation due to interface debonding. Furthermore, this damage degradation function could lead to the descriptions of cohesive interface failure and bulk brittle/cohesive crack in the unified framework. Our model could also simulate the brittle interface failure when the degradation function recovers the classical one by adopting the specific parameters. We present several numerical examples for numerical validation and applications in the cohesive interface failure problems.

This article is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the proposed phase-field formulations. Section 3 states the numerical solution strategy. Section 4 provides two benchmark examples of interface failure to validate our model, while Section 5 shows numerical applications into several other interface problems. Finally, concluding remarks are drawn in Section 6

2. Phase-field formulations for interface failure

This section outlines our phase-field formulations for interface failure analysis. Section 2.1 states the numerical hypothesis in our model. Section 2.2 and Section 2.3 derives the theoretical formulations of phase-field regularization in bulk and interface regions, respectively. Section 2.4 devotes to the phase-field variational formulations of a general cracked body with internal interfaces. Governing equations of our new phase-field model for cohesive interface failure analysis are summarized in Section 2.5.

2.1. Numerical hypothesis

We consider an arbitrary computational domain Ω bounded by $\partial\Omega$, which is divided into displacement-prescribed boundary $\partial\Omega_u$ and the traction-prescribed one $\partial\Omega_t$. Two kinds of boundaries have the following relations: (i) $\partial\Omega = \partial\Omega_t \cup \partial\Omega_u$, and (ii) $\partial\Omega_t \cap \partial\Omega_u = \emptyset$. In our model, two kinds of discontinuities Γ are postulated in the computational domain, including the diffuse cracks Γ_d and discrete interfaces Γ_i , with the following relation $\Gamma = \Gamma_i \cup \Gamma_d$. The computational domain Ω is assumed to be separated into two non-overlapping subdomains Ω_1 and Ω_2 by the prescribed interface Γ_i in bimaterials or multimaterials, as shown in Fig. 1. Moreover, we also divided the computational domain Ω into the bulk region Ω_b and interface region Ω_i .

According to the variational principle in continuum mechanics [40, 41], the total potential energy function $\Pi(\epsilon, \Gamma)$ can be written as

$$\Pi(\epsilon, \Gamma) = \Psi_{int}(\epsilon, \Gamma) - \mathcal{W}_{ext}(\mathbf{u}) = \Psi_{\Omega}(\epsilon) + \Psi_{\Gamma_d}(\Gamma_d) + \Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i) - \mathcal{W}_{ext}(\mathbf{u}) \quad (1)$$

where $\Psi_{int}(\epsilon, \Gamma)$ is the internal energy function, which is defined as the sum of the stored elastic strain energy $\Psi_{\Omega}(\epsilon)$ and the dissipated/released energy through two different potential mechanisms, including bulk fracture released energy $\Psi_{\Gamma_d}(\Gamma_d)$ and interface fracture dissipated energy $\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i)$, and $\mathcal{W}_{ext}(\mathbf{u})$ denotes the external loading work.

Picking up the idea by Paggi's group [21,30], we divided the dissipated energies into two kinds, i.e., $\Psi_{\Gamma_d}(\Gamma_d)$ and $\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i)$, which stem from bulk cracking in matrix and interface debonding, respectively. In our model, the cohesive interface failure driving forces are consistently derived, which include two new features: (i) the employment of bulk cracking driving forces for mixed-mode fracture phenomena proposed in [51], and (ii) incorporation of a cohesive traction–separation–damage law on the zero-thickness interface elements by a proposed parameterized degradation function instead of the classical CZM.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of (a) an arbitrary computational domain Ω with diffuse cracks Γ_d and discrete interfaces Γ_i ; (b) diffuse crack regularized solution in 1D case; (c) the cohesive traction–separation law on the discrete interface.

2.2. Phase-field regularization in bulk region

In the phase-field framework [40,41,49], the elastic strain energy function in the bulk region $\Psi_b(\epsilon, \Gamma_d)$ consists of stored elastic strain energy function $\Psi_{\Omega_b}(\epsilon)$ and the bulk cracking released energy function $\Psi_{\Gamma_d}(\Gamma_d)$. The variational bulk energy function can be approximated as [41,49]

$$\Psi_b(\epsilon, \Gamma_d) = \Psi_{\Omega_b}(\epsilon) + \Psi_{\Gamma_d}(\Gamma_d) \simeq \int_{\Omega_b \setminus \Gamma_d} \psi_{\ell_b}(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) d\Omega_b + \int_{\Gamma_d} G_c d\Gamma_d \quad (2)$$

where $\psi_{\ell_b}(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d)$ denotes the stored elastic strain energy density, and G_c is the critical fracture energy release rate of the bulk material. Introducing the bulk free energy density function $\psi_b(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d, \nabla d)$, Eq. (2) is written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_b(\epsilon, \Gamma_d) &\simeq \int_{\Omega_b} \psi_b(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d, \nabla d) d\Omega_b \\ &= \int_{\Omega_b} \psi_{\ell_b}(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) d\Omega_b + \int_{\Omega_b} G_c \gamma_b(d, \nabla d) d\Omega_b \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

which indicates

$$\psi_b(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d, \nabla d) = \psi_{\ell_b}(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) + G_c \gamma(d, \nabla d) \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is the strain tensor, ℓ_b is the internal length scale in bulk regions and $\gamma_b(d, \nabla d)$ denotes the discontinuous surface density function in the bulk region, which reads

$$\gamma_b(d, \nabla d) = \frac{1}{2\ell_b} d^2 + \frac{\ell_b}{2} |\nabla d|^2 \quad (5)$$

Based on the volumetric–deviatoric splitting strategy in phase-field approach [50,51], the strain tensor ϵ is decomposed into the volumetric and deviatoric strain tensor, i.e., $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{sph}} + \epsilon_{\text{dev}}$. Considering the pure tensile fracture, pure shear fracture and mixed-mode tensile/compressive-shear fracture in bulk regions, the stored elastic strain energy density is assumed as

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\ell_b}(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) &= \psi_n^+(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) + \psi_n^-(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) + \psi_t(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}), d) \\ &= g_b(d) [\psi_n^+(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) + \psi_t(\epsilon(\mathbf{u}))] + \psi_n^-(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $g_b(d)$ is the standard degradation function with the constant k in phase-field framework [49], ψ_n^+ , ψ_n^- and ψ_t are the volumetric dilation, volumetric compression and purely deviatoric parts of stored elastic strain energy densities, respectively.

$$\psi_n^+(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\text{sph}}^+(\mathbf{u}) : \mathbb{C} : \epsilon_{\text{sph}}^+(\mathbf{u}) \quad (7a)$$

$$\psi_n^-(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\text{sph}}^-(\mathbf{u}) : \mathbb{C} : \epsilon_{\text{sph}}^-(\mathbf{u}) \quad (7b)$$

$$\psi_t(\epsilon(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\text{dev}}(\mathbf{u}) : \mathbb{C} : \epsilon_{\text{dev}}(\mathbf{u}) \quad (7c)$$

where \mathbb{C} is the fourth-order stiffness tensor, $\epsilon_{\text{sph}}^\pm$ and ϵ_{dev} are the volumetric and deviatoric strain tensors, which read

$$\epsilon_{\text{sph}}^\pm(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{3} \langle \text{tr}(\epsilon(\nabla \mathbf{u})) \rangle_\pm \mathbf{I} \quad (8a)$$

$$\epsilon_{\text{dev}}(\mathbf{u}) = \epsilon(\nabla \mathbf{u}) - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\epsilon(\nabla \mathbf{u})) \mathbf{I} \quad (8b)$$

in which \mathbf{I} represents the second-order identity tensor, $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ is the trace operator and $\langle \cdot \rangle_\pm = (\cdot \pm |\cdot|)/2$ is the bracket operator.

2.3. Cohesive traction–separation–damage in interface region

According to our numerical hypothesis, the dissipated energy $\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i)$ contributes to the interface failure process along the prescribed interfaces of the cracked brittle/quasi-brittle solids. To describe the gradual stiffness reduction in the interface region, in our model, we take the current interface damage states into consideration for both brittle/cohesive traction–separation–damage responses during the interface failure process. In this sense, the interface fracture dissipated energy $\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i)$ is regularized as

$$\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Gamma_i) \simeq \Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\Delta(\mathbf{u}), d) = \int_{\Gamma_i} g_i(d) \psi_i(\Delta(\mathbf{u})) d\Gamma_i + \int_{\Gamma_i} G_i d\Gamma_i \quad (9)$$

where $\Delta(\mathbf{u})$ is the displacement jump across the interface Γ_i , and G_i is the critical interface fracture energy release rate.

Remark 1. It is worth noting that this model is different from the previous phase-field CZM formulations [21,62], where the simple tension cut-off interface model is employed to describe the variations of interface stiffness. Furthermore, our model is also different from the most recent reports on phase-field CZM for modeling delamination induced by matrix cracking [30], where crack opening is coupled with damage states for describing the gradual stiffness reduction from interface failure up to the complete decohesion. The requirement of internal variables in [30] results in the complex calibration procedures of parameters. Our model decouples the interface damage state and separation in the traction–separation–damage laws on zero-thickness elements. The relevant parameters for describing mechanical responses of interface debonding are convenient to be determined based on the experimental data.

Similarly, the discontinuous surface density function of interface $\gamma_i(d, \nabla d)$ reads

$$\gamma_i(d, \nabla d) = \frac{1}{2\ell_i} d^2 + \frac{\ell_i}{2} |\nabla d|^2 \quad (10)$$

where ℓ_i is the internal length scale of interfaces. Considering the volumetric dilatation, volumetric compression and pure deviatoric deformation on interfaces, the regularized formation of interface fracture dissipated energy is written as

$$\Psi_{\Gamma_i}(\mathbf{\Delta}, d) = \int_{\Gamma_i} g_i(d) \left[\psi_{i,n}^+(\mathbf{\Delta}) + \psi_{i,t}(\mathbf{\Delta}) \right] + \psi_{i,n}^-(\mathbf{\Delta}) d\Gamma_i + \int_{\Omega_i} \mathcal{G}_i \gamma_i(d, \nabla d) d\Omega_i \quad (11)$$

where $\psi_{i,n}^+$, $\psi_{i,n}^-$ and $\psi_{i,t}$ represent the volumetric dilatation, volumetric compression and pure deviatoric components of the interface dissipated energy density, respectively, which are formulated as

$$\psi_{i,n}^+(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} k_n \cdot \langle \Delta_n(\mathbf{u}) \rangle_+^2 \quad (12a)$$

$$\psi_{i,n}^-(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} k_n \cdot \langle \Delta_n(\mathbf{u}) \rangle_-^2 \quad (12b)$$

$$\psi_{i,t}(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) = \frac{1}{2} k_t \cdot \Delta_t(\mathbf{u})^2 \quad (12c)$$

where k_n and k_t represent the interface stiffness in the normal and tangential directions, i.e., \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{m} , respectively (see Fig. 1a); $\Delta_n(\mathbf{u})$ and $\Delta_t(\mathbf{u})$ are the normal and tangential components of the interface separation, respectively.

In our phase-field modeling framework, the relative displacement components across the prescribed interface Γ_i are calculated as

$$\Delta_n(\mathbf{u}) = h \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} : (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}) \quad (13a)$$

$$\Delta_t(\mathbf{u}) = h \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} : (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{m}) \quad (13b)$$

where h is the thickness of FE meshes along the prescribed interface Γ_i .

Remark 2. This volumetric-deviatoric splitting numerical strategy for the interface elements enables only considering the relative displacements along the normal and tangential directions of interfaces, while it does not take the lateral deformation into consideration. Thus, this strategy could avoid the effects of interface elementary thickness, which aims at achieving inserting zero-thickness interface elements in our phase-field model for interface failure modeling.

To describe the nonlinear mechanical responses of interfaces, we propose a new energetic degradation function in the phase-field framework. The new energetic degradation function is expressed in the following quadratic reciprocal form, which enables to capture the strain softening behaviors of composite materials during interface failure process.

$$g_i(d) = \left(\frac{\delta_0}{(1-d)\delta_0 + d\delta_1} \right)^2 + (\chi + \pi)d^2 - (\chi + 2\pi)d \quad (14a)$$

$$\chi = 2 \left[(\delta_1 - \delta_0) \delta_0^2 \right] / \delta_1^3 \quad (14b)$$

$$\pi = \delta_0^2 / \delta_1^2 \quad (14c)$$

where δ_0 and δ_1 are interface parameters related to the peak critical and ultimate values of interface separations.

To show the difference between our new energetic degradation function and the previous ones [41,87–89], we plot the various degradation functions at the post-failure regime in Fig. 2(a). It is worth mentioning that the parameters in most of the previous degradation functions are statistic values, which require the mathematical data fitting techniques. However, in our model, the interface parameters can be identified from the laboratory testing results, i.e., ratio of critical gap δ_1/δ_0 . To perform the effect δ_1/δ_0 on $g_i(d)$, we depict degradation curves for different ratios in Fig. 2(b). We observe that $g_i(d)$ curves become closer to the classical one [21,41,87] as δ_1/δ_0 decreases. When $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 1.0$, our new $g_i(d)$ would recover to the classical one for brittle fracture.

To ensure the consistency of degradation functions in both bulk and interface regions, the following necessary constraints should be satisfied.

$$g_b(d) = g_i(d) = (1-d)^2 \quad \delta_0 = \delta_1 \quad (15a)$$

$$g_b(d) = g_i(d) = g'_c(d) = g'_i(d) = 0 \quad d = 1 \quad (15b)$$

$$g_b(d) = g_i(d) = 1 \quad d = 0 \quad (15c)$$

2.4. Phase-field variational formulation

Referring to the variation principle, the total potential energy function for the arbitrary cracked domain with the prescribed interfaces in Eq. (1) is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi(\mathbf{u}, d, \nabla d) = & \int_{\Omega_b} \psi_{\ell_b}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}), d) d\Omega_b + \int_{\Omega_b} \mathcal{G}_c \gamma_b(d, \nabla d) d\Omega_b \\ & + \int_{\Omega_i} \mathcal{G}_i \gamma_i(d, \nabla d) d\Omega_i \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_i} g_i(d) \left[\psi_{i,n}^+(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) + \psi_{i,t}(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) \right] + \psi_{i,n}^-(\mathbf{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) d\Gamma_i \\ & - \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{u} d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega} \bar{\mathbf{t}} \cdot \mathbf{u} dS \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{b} is the body force vector, and $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ denotes the prescribed traction.

Based on Hamilton's principle, Lagrange density \mathcal{L} of this system has the following relationship

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, d, \dot{d}, \nabla d) d\Omega = \mathcal{K}(\dot{\mathbf{u}}) + \mathcal{V}(d) + \Pi(\mathbf{u}, d, \nabla d) \quad (17)$$

where $\mathcal{K}(\dot{\mathbf{u}})$ is the kinematic energy and $\mathcal{V}(d)$ is viscous dissipation energy, which can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{K}(\dot{\mathbf{u}}) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} \rho \dot{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}} d\Omega \quad (18)$$

$$\mathcal{V}(d) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{\mathcal{G}_c}{\ell_b} \zeta d d\Omega \quad (19)$$

in which ρ is material density, $\zeta = \eta d$ denotes the viscous crack resistance and η is the viscous parameter controlling numerical stability during phase-field evolution.

Thus, this variational problem is solved by Hamilton's principle:

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{u}, \dot{\mathbf{u}}, d, \dot{d}, \nabla d) d\Omega dt = 0 \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \quad (20)$$

where $\delta \mathcal{L}$ is the variational form of Lagrange density.

We then obtain the Euler–Lagrange equation as

$$\delta \mathcal{L} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} \cdot \delta \dot{\mathbf{u}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} : \delta \nabla \mathbf{u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d} \cdot \delta d + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{d}} \cdot \delta \dot{d} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} : \delta \nabla d = 0 \quad (21)$$

which can be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \mathcal{L} = & \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \right) - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d} \cdot \delta d \\ & + \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right) \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} + \text{div} \left(\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right)^T \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} \right) - \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \right) \cdot \delta d \\ & + \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \cdot \delta d \right) + \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{d}} \cdot \delta \dot{d} \right) - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{d}} \cdot \delta \dot{d} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Integrating $\delta \mathcal{L}$ over Ω and $[t_1, t_2]$ and applying divergence theorem, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \delta \mathcal{L} d\Omega dt = & \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \left[-\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} - \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right) + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \right] \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega dt \\ & + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \left[-\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{d}} - \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \right) + \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d} \right] \cdot \delta d d\Omega dt \\ & + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right)^T \cdot \mathbf{n} \cdot \delta \mathbf{u} d\Omega dt \\ & + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \cdot \delta d d\Omega dt \\ & + \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{d}} \cdot \delta \dot{d} \right) \Big|_{t_1}^{t_2} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} \cdot \delta \dot{\mathbf{u}} \right) \Big|_{t_1}^{t_2} d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Then, we obtain the Euler–Lagrange equations of this variational problem as follows

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}} + \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right) - \mathbf{b} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (24a)$$

Fig. 2. (a) Comparison of energetic degradation function $g_i(d)$ in different phase-field models [41,87–89]; and (b) the effect of critical gap ratio δ_i/δ_0 on $g_i(d)$ in our model.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d} + \text{div} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial d} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (24b)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla \mathbf{u}} \right)^T \cdot \mathbf{n} + \bar{\mathbf{i}} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial \Omega_t \quad (24c)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \nabla d} \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial \Omega \cup \Gamma \quad (24d)$$

2.5. Phase-field governing equations for interface failure

Recalling the explicit formulation of $\delta \mathcal{L}$ in Eq. (21), the governing equations of quasi-static equilibrium are written as

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) + \mathbf{b} = \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus \Gamma_i \quad (25)$$

$$\mathcal{T}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\mathbf{u}), d) + \mathbf{b} = \rho \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_i \quad (26)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}, d) \cdot \mathbf{n} = \bar{\mathbf{i}} \quad \text{on } \partial \Omega_t \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} \quad \text{on } \partial \Omega_u \quad (28)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d)$ is the effective stress tensor in the bulk region, and \mathcal{T} represents the cohesive traction in the interface region, which are derived as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, d) = \frac{\partial \psi_{\ell_b}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u}), d)}{\partial \mathbf{u}} = g_b(d) \mathbb{C} : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{sph}}^+ + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{dev}}) + \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{sph}}^- \quad (29)$$

and

$$\mathcal{T}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\mathbf{u}), d) = \frac{\partial \psi_i(\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\mathbf{u}), d)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\Delta}} = g_i(d) \mathbb{K} \cdot [\Delta_r, \langle \Delta_n \rangle_+]^T + \mathbb{K} \cdot [0, \langle \Delta_n \rangle_-]^T \quad (30)$$

where \mathbb{K} is the interface stiffness matrix.

Similarly, using Eq. (21), we derive the following phase-field evolution for interface failure analysis.

$$g'_b(d) (\psi_n^+ + \psi_t) - \frac{G_c}{\ell_b} d + \ell_b G_c \nabla^2 d = \frac{G_c}{\ell_b} \eta d \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus \Gamma_i \quad (31)$$

$$g'_i(d) (\psi_{i,n}^+ + \psi_{i,t}) - \frac{G_i}{\ell_i} d + \ell_i G_i \nabla^2 d = \frac{G_i}{\ell_i} \eta d \quad \text{on } \Gamma_i \quad (32)$$

$$\nabla d \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial \Omega \cup \Gamma \quad (33)$$

where G_i is the critical fracture energy release rate of interfaces.

Thus, the new failure driving forces \mathcal{H} for both bulk fracture and interface failure are expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_n = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{ \psi_n^+(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})) \} \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \geq 0 \quad \mathcal{H}_{i,n} = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{ \psi_{i,n}^+(\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) \} \quad \Delta_n \geq 0 \quad (34a)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_n = 0 \quad \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) < 0 \quad \mathcal{H}_{i,n} = 0 \quad \Delta_n < 0 \quad (34b)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_t = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{ \psi_t(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\mathbf{u})) \} \quad \mathcal{H}_{i,t} = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \{ \psi_{i,t}(\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\mathbf{u})) \} \quad (34c)$$

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration of mixed-mode interface failure in the proposed phase-field framework.

Now, phase-field evolution for both bulk fracture and interface failure is recast into

$$g'_c(d) \ell_b (\mathcal{H}_n + \mathcal{H}_t) / G_c - d + \ell_b^2 \nabla^2 d = \eta d \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus \Gamma_i \quad (35)$$

$$g'_i(d) \ell_i (\mathcal{H}_{i,n} + \mathcal{H}_{i,t}) / G_i - d + \ell_i^2 \nabla^2 d = \eta d \quad \text{on } \Gamma_i \quad (36)$$

When we consider the mixed-mode failure in bulk regions and interfaces, referring to our previous work [51], the general version of phase-field evolution can be written as

$$g'_c(d) \ell_b \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{G_c^I} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{G_c^{II}} \right) \alpha - d + \ell_b^2 \nabla^2 d = \eta d \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus \Gamma_i \quad (37)$$

$$g'_i(d) \ell_i \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_{i,n}}{G_i^I} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_{i,t}}{G_i^{II}} \right) \xi - d + \ell_i^2 \nabla^2 d = \eta d \quad \text{on } \Gamma_i \quad (38)$$

where G_c^I and G_c^{II} are the critical fracture energy release rates for mode-I and mode-II fracture in bulk regions, and G_i^I and G_i^{II} are the critical fracture energy release rates for tensile and shear modes on interface, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3. The parameters α and ξ are

$$\alpha = \frac{(\mathcal{H}_n + \mathcal{H}_t) G_c^I G_c^{II}}{G_c (\mathcal{H}_t G_c^I + \mathcal{H}_n G_c^{II})} \quad \xi = \frac{(\mathcal{H}_{i,n} + \mathcal{H}_{i,t}) G_i^I G_i^{II}}{G_i (\mathcal{H}_{i,t} G_i^I + \mathcal{H}_{i,n} G_i^{II})} \quad (39)$$

3. Finite element solution strategy

This section details the numerical solution strategy pursued to address interface failure analyses by our model. The computational

Fig. 4. (a) Sketch of the interface finite element topology in a 2D case, and (b) details of a interface element and a bulk element.

domain Ω is divided into two non-overlapping regions, including bulk region Ω_b and interface region Ω_i , with $\Omega = \Omega_b \cup \Omega_i$, as shown in Fig. 4(a). In FEM framework, the displacement and phase-field variables $\{u, d\}$ and their gradients $\{\nabla u, \nabla d\}$ are approximated as follows:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathcal{N}_I^u(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_I(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \nabla \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathcal{B}_I^u(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_I(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (40a)$$

$$d(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathcal{N}_I^d(\mathbf{x}) \cdot d_I(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \nabla d(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^n \mathcal{B}_I^d(\mathbf{x}) \cdot d_I(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (40b)$$

where \mathbf{u}_I and d_I are displacement and phase-field variables at the node \mathbf{x}_I ; n denotes the number of nodes in a bulk/interface element; \mathcal{N}_I^u and \mathcal{N}_I^d are the standard C^0 -continuous shape functions for the displacement and phase-field variables; \mathcal{B}_I^u is the displacement-strain operator, and \mathcal{B}_I^d is the gradient operator for phase-field d .

The standard C^0 -continuous shape functions for \mathbf{u} and d in 2D plane strain cases are written as

$$\mathcal{N}^u = \begin{bmatrix} N_1 & 0 & \dots & N_n & 0 \\ 0 & N_1 & \dots & 0 & N_n \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{N}^d = [N_1 \quad \dots \quad N_n] \quad (41)$$

Similarly, the derivative matrices for \mathbf{u} and d are expressed as

$$\mathcal{B}^u = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1,x} & 0 & \dots & N_{n,x} & 0 \\ 0 & N_{1,y} & \dots & 0 & N_{n,y} \\ N_{1,y} & N_{1,x} & \dots & N_{n,y} & N_{n,x} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{B}^d = \begin{bmatrix} N_{1,x} & \dots & N_{n,x} \\ N_{1,y} & \dots & N_{n,y} \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

In our model, we adopt Gaussian quadrature points in the bulk finite element, while we employ two quadrature points on the middle line, i.e., line $N1'-N2'$, in the interface finite element, as shown in Fig. 4(b).

In order to evaluate the displacement gap Δ at any point inside the interface finite element, we need to collect the displacements of the four interface finite element nodes. The relative displacements within the interface finite element are calculated by the differences between \mathbf{u} at $N1$ and $N2$ with respect to those at $N4$ and $N3$ in Fig. 4(b). Considering the transformation between global reference system $x-y$ and the local reference system of interface finite element $m-n$, the tangential and normal gaps Δ_t and Δ_n are determined by the multiplication with the rotation matrix \mathcal{R} . Thus, the displacement gap Δ within the interface finite element is calculated as

$$\Delta(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{I=1}^{n=4} \mathcal{B}_I^i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathcal{R} \cdot \mathbf{u}_I(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (43)$$

where \mathcal{B}_I^i is the interface compatibility operator, and \mathcal{R} represents the rotation matrix related to the principle direction θ of the interface finite

element, see Fig. 4(b). The explicit formulations are

$$\mathcal{B}^i = \begin{bmatrix} -N_1 & 0 & -N_2 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_1 & 0 \\ 0 & -N_1 & 0 & -N_2 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (44)$$

and

$$\mathcal{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

The spatio-temporal discrete equations for the quasi-static equations of equilibrium and the phase-field evolution are obtained from the standard Galerkin approximation

$$\mathcal{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} = \mathcal{F}_{ext}(\mathbf{u}) - \mathcal{F}_{int}(\mathbf{u}, d) \quad (46)$$

$$\mathcal{C}\dot{d} = \mathcal{Y}(d, \nabla d, \mathcal{H}) \quad (47)$$

Explicit expressions for these matrices are as follows:

- Mass matrix:

$$\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} \mathcal{N}_e^{uT} \rho \mathcal{N}_e^u d\Omega_e \quad (48)$$

where N_e is the number of elements in the computational domain, Ω_e is the domain of e th element and $\mathcal{A}_{e=1}^{N_e}$ is the assembly operator

- External force matrix:

$$\mathcal{F}_{ext}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} \mathcal{N}_e^{uT} \mathbf{b} d\Omega_e + \mathcal{A} \int_{\partial\Omega_e^t} \mathcal{N}_e^{uT} \bar{\mathbf{t}} d\Gamma_e \quad (49)$$

where N_e^t is the number of elements where the prescribed traction is applied, and $\partial\Omega_e^t$ denotes the prescribed traction boundary in the e th element.

- Internal force matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{int}(\mathbf{u}, d) = & \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} \left[g_b(d) (\mathcal{B}_e^u)^T \mathbb{C} (\epsilon_{sph}^+ + \epsilon_{dev}) + (\mathcal{B}_e^u)^T \mathbb{C} \epsilon_{sph}^- \right] d\Omega_e \\ & + \mathcal{A} \int_{\Gamma_i} \left[g_i(d) (\mathcal{B}_e^i)^T \mathbb{K} (\Delta_t, \langle \Delta_n \rangle_+) \right. \\ & \left. + (\mathcal{B}_e^i)^T \mathbb{K} (\Delta_t, \langle \Delta_n \rangle_-) \right] d\Gamma_i \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where \mathbb{C} is the stress-strain matrix for the bulk region and \mathbb{K} represents tangent constitutive operator of the interface region.

- Viscous matrix:

$$\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} (\mathcal{N}_e^d)^T \eta \mathcal{N}_e^d d\Omega_e \quad (51)$$

Fig. 5. Computational flowchart and algorithmic overview of our new phase-field model for cohesive interface failure analysis.

where η is the viscous parameter.

- Failure dissipation matrix:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{Y}(d, \nabla d, \mathcal{H}) = & \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} \left[2\alpha \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_n}{G_c^I} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_t}{G_c^{II}} \right) (\mathcal{N}_e^d)^T (1-d) \right] d\Omega_e \\
 & + \mathcal{A} \int_{\Gamma_i} \left(\frac{\mathcal{H}_{i,n}}{G_c^I} + \frac{\mathcal{H}_{i,t}}{G_c^{II}} \right) \xi (\mathcal{N}_e^d)^T \\
 & \cdot \left[\frac{2(\delta_1 - \delta_0) \delta_0^2}{[(1-d)\delta_0 + d\delta_1]^3} + 2(\chi + \pi)d - (\chi + 2\pi) \right] d\Gamma_i \\
 & - \mathcal{A} \int_{\Omega_e} \left[(\mathcal{N}_e^d)^T d - \ell_b^2 (\mathcal{B}_e^d)^T d \right] d\Omega_e \\
 & - \mathcal{A} \int_{\Gamma_i} \left[(\mathcal{N}_e^d)^T d - \ell_i^2 (\mathcal{B}_e^d)^T d \right] d\Gamma_i
 \end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

The staggered time integration scheme is employed to calculate the displacement fields and phase-field evolution. Taking the time interval $[T_r, T_{r+1}]$ with $\Delta t = T_{r+1} - T_r$, the displacement fields can be obtained by the following explicit central-difference integration scheme.

$$\ddot{u}^t = \mathcal{M}^{-1} [\mathcal{F}_{ext}^t(u^t) - \mathcal{F}_{int}^t(u^t, d^t)] \tag{53a}$$

$$\dot{u}^{t+\frac{1}{2}} = \dot{u}^{t-\frac{1}{2}} + \Delta t \ddot{u}^t \tag{53b}$$

$$u^{t+1} = u^t + \Delta t \dot{u}^{t+\frac{1}{2}} \tag{53c}$$

While the phase-field evolution is computed using the explicit forward-difference time-integration strategy as follows:

$$\dot{d}^t = C^{-1} \cdot \mathcal{Y}(d^t, \nabla d^t, \mathcal{H}^t) \tag{54a}$$

$$d^{t+1} = d^t + \Delta t \dot{d}^t \tag{54b}$$

Moreover, the initial values of displacement fields and phase-field variable are

$$u^0 = \bar{u} \quad d^0 = \bar{d} \tag{55a}$$

$$\dot{u}^{\pm\frac{1}{2}} = \dot{u}^0 \pm \frac{\Delta t}{2} \ddot{u}^0 \quad \dot{d}^0 = \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial t} \tag{55b}$$

The computational flowchart and the algorithmic overview of our new phase-field model for cohesive interface failure analysis are plotted in Fig. 5. The staggered time integration scheme bypasses the assembling of global stiffness matrix for quasi-static solutions, which shows the highly efficient performance in the enormous matrix manipulation.

4. Benchmark problems

To validate our model for cohesive interface failure analyses, we present two benchmark problems, including (i) the square plate with horizontal interface, and (ii) mode-I delamination test. We carry out the first numerical simulation under 2D plane-strain assumption and the second one under 3D case.

Fig. 6. Schematic diagram of a square plate with a horizontal interface: (a) geometry and boundaries, and (b) finite element discretization.

Fig. 7. The cohesive interface failure process of a square plate with a horizontal interface.

4.1. Square plate with horizontal interface

We first consider a square plate with one horizontal interface at mid-height in the constant strain patch test [31,90]. The square plate has the side length $L = 1.0$ mm. The vertical and horizontal displacements are constrained at the bottom boundary, while the constant incremental displacement $\Delta u_y = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mm/s is applied on the top boundary, as shown in Fig. 6(a). The square computational domain is composed of 240 bulk finite elements and 20 finite interface elements, as depicted in Fig. 6(b). Furthermore, the associated mechanical parameters are assumed as follows: Young's modulus $E = 7.20$ MPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.33$, interface stiffness $k_n = 36.0$ kPa and $k_t = 0.0$ kPa, material density $\rho = 2,450$ kg/m³, viscous parameter $\eta = 0.1$ ms, bulk mode-I fracture energy release rate $G_c^I = 1.0$ J/m², bulk mode-II fracture energy release rate $G_c^{II} = 1.0$ J/m², interface fracture energy release rates $G_i^I = 0.02$ J/m² for mode-I, and $G_i^{II} = 0.2$ J/m² for mode-II. We also assume the internal length scales as $\ell_b = \ell_i = 0.1$ mm.

To present the cohesive interface failure process, Figs. 7(a)–(d) show the spatiotemporal distributions of the phase-field variable d in the square plate with a horizontal interface subjected to the uniaxial tension. We observe that the damage is gradually accumulated in the interface region until the complete failure as the prescribed vertical displacement increases.

Fig. 8(a) plots the global mechanical response of this plate, i.e., force–displacement curve, during the cohesive interface failure process.

Fig. 8. Comparison of (a) global mechanical responses and (b) degradation function evolution obtained from the standard phase-field model [41], our model and the hybrid phase-field CZM [21].

To verify the accuracy of our model, we compare the predicted mechanical responses obtained from our new model with those obtained from the standard phase-field model [41] and the hybrid phase-field CZM [21]. Fig. 8(a) indicates that our present numerical results are close to the data obtained from the previous hybrid phase-field CZM in both pre- and post-failure regimes. It is worth noting that the standard phase-field model [41] employs the same degradation function for bulk and interface regions, while the hybrid phase-field CZM [21] adopts the empirical formulations with tension cut-off law, as shown in Fig. 8(b). Furthermore, because of the new energetic degradation function in our model, the present numerical results overcome the unphysical jumps in the previous ones. This new feature enables our model to effectively address the cohesive interface failure without some ill-posed numerical oscillation.

The critical gap ratio δ_1/δ_0 plays an important role in our model to simulate the cohesive interface failure behaviors. To perform the capability of our model, we study the effect of different δ_1/δ_0 on the global mechanical responses of the square plate with a horizontal interface under uniform tension. Four different δ_1/δ_0 ratios, i.e., $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 1.0$, $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 5.0$, $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 10.0$, and $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 20.0$ are employed in numerical simulations. Fig. 9(a) plots the four various force–displacement curves, while the effect of the critical gap ratio δ_1/δ_0 on the released interface fracture energy in the square plates is depicted in Fig. 9(b). We observe that the strain-softening behaviors of cohesive interface failure become pronounced as δ_1/δ_0 increases, which also affects the total released interface fracture energy.

To study the effect of characteristic length scales on the cohesive interface failure patterns and global mechanical responses, three numerical samples with the fixed element size (see Fig. 6b) and different internal characteristic length scales, i.e., $\ell_b = \ell_i = 0.20$ mm, $\ell_b = \ell_i = 0.10$ mm, and $\ell_b = \ell_i = 0.05$ mm, are employed in our modified phase-field modeling. The critical gap ratio $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 10.0$ is adopted in these three numerical simulations. Fig. 10(a) and Fig. 10(b) show the ultimately cohesive interface failure patterns and global mechanical responses, respectively. It can be observed from Fig. 10(a) that the cohesive interface failure pattern in these three numerical samples are

Fig. 9. Effect of critical gap ratio δ_i/δ_0 on (a) the global mechanical responses and (b) the released interface fracture energy.

Fig. 10. Effect of characteristic length scales on (a) the cohesive interface failure patterns and (b) global mechanical responses.

similar. With the increase of ℓ_b and ℓ_i , the thickness of cohesive interface failure pattern increases, as observed from Fig. 10(a). Fig. 10(b) presents that the global mechanical responses, i.e., axial force — axial displacement curves, in these three numerical samples are close to each other. These numerical phenomena demonstrates the numerical convergence of our modified phase-field models. The recent studies on cohesive phase-field models [85,86] have demonstrated the potential for these models to address both bulk and interface failure in quasi-brittle materials. These studies have also investigated length scale and mesh orientation sensitivity in these models.

4.2. Mode-I delamination test

We further consider an asymmetric double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen for the mode-I delamination test. The testing DCB specimen consists of two bonded cantilever beams with 350.0 mm in length, 24.0 mm in height and 80.0 mm in width. The initial crack with 100.0 mm in length is set on the middle line, as illustrated in Fig. 11(a). The crack opening load is applied at the pre-crack end by the prescribed constant displacement rate of $\dot{u}_y = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mm/s. Referring to [91], we assume the following values of mechanical properties in 3D simulations, mass density $\rho = 2,450$ kg/m³, Young's modulus $E = 9.0$ GPa,

Poisson ratio $\nu = 0.3$, interface stiffness $k_n = 9.0$ GPa, viscous parameter $\eta = 0.1$ ms, critical bulk fracture energy release rate $G_c^I = 2.0 \times 10^4$ J/m² = $0.1G_c^{II}$, critical interface fracture energy release rates $G_i^I = 145.0$ J/m², $G_i^{II} = 1000.0$ J/m² and critical gap ratio $\delta_i/\delta_0 = 4.2$. The characteristic length scale in the present phase-field simulations are $\ell_b = 10.0$ mm and $\ell_i = 4.0$ mm, respectively. The 3D computational domain is discretized into 11,200 bulk elements and 1,120 interface elements, as shown in Fig. 11(b).

Fig. 12(a) compares the load-crack opening displacement (P-COD) curves for the simulated DCB specimen with the laboratory experimental measurements [91]. To demonstrate the robustness of our model, we study the mesh sensitivity and numerical convergence. Three numerical DCB specimens with different element length h_e (see Fig. 11b) are simulated in 3D cases, where values of h_e are adopted as 2.5 mm, 5.0 mm and 10.0 mm. We observe that our phase-field numerical results are in agreement with the reported experimental data. The numerical predictions of P-COD curves in three specimens are close to each other. Fig. 12(a) also shows that the numerical P-COD curve becomes closer to laboratory experimental observations as h_e decreases. Moreover, good agreement of the ultimately cohesive interface failure can be observed between the previous experimental observations [91] and our present predictions.

To further explore the onset of cohesive interface failure in this mode-I delamination test, we plot the distributions of phase-field variable d , normal gap δ_n , degradation function $g_i(d)$ and normal traction \mathcal{T}_n along the interface in a DCB specimen in Figs. 13(a)–(d), respectively. We observe that the cohesive interface failure process can be characterized by three segments, including elastic zone, fracture process zone and crack extension zone. We also find the related relationships among d , δ_n , $g_i(d)$ and \mathcal{T}_n . The evolution of d , δ_n and $g_i(d)$ all contribute to the nonlinear traction–separation behaviors of cohesive interface failure process. The normal traction reaches the peak value around the boundary between elastic zone and fracture process zone, and behaves strain-softening phenomena in the fracture process zones.

5. Numerical applications

In this section, we also carry out two numerical applications involving (i) a peeling test on bi-material plates and (ii) crack impinging on interfaces to further demonstrate the capability and performance of our new phase-field model for cohesive interface failure in quasi-brittle solids.

Fig. 11. Schematic diagram of a DCB specimen for the mode-I delamination test: (a) geometry and boundary conditions, and (b) finite element discretization.

Fig. 12. Comparison of DCB specimens for mode-I delamination test: (a) P-COD curves against [91], (b) experimental observations [91] and (c) our 3D numerical predictions.

5.1. Example-I: A peeling test on a bimaterial plate

We first apply to simulate a peeling test on a bi-material plate composed of two blocks with the same length of 2.0 mm and different heights. The lower block has the height of 0.15 mm, whereas the upper block has a height of 1.0 mm, as shown in Fig. 14(a). We observe from Fig. 14(b) that two blocks are discretized into 250 bulk finite elements, while 25 zero-thickness interface finite elements are placed between these two blocks. The bulk and interface finite elements are rectangular with h_e in length and h_b in width. The maximum and minimum values of h_b are $h_b^{\max} = 0.2$ mm and $h_b^{\min} = 0.005$ mm, respectively. Based on the literature [92,93], both material \mathcal{M}_1 in upper block and material \mathcal{M}_2 in lower block have a vanishing Poisson's ratio and simulations are carried out under 2D plane strain assumption. The upper block has Young's modulus $E_1 = 5.0$ MPa to model the highly deformable elastomeric tape, while the lower one has Young's modulus $E_2 = 500.0$ MPa for the rigid substrate. In addition, some other mechanical parameters in this peeling test are summarized as follows: interface stiffness $k_n = 10.0$ GPa, material density $\rho_{\mathcal{M}_1} = 2,450$ kg/m³ & $\rho_{\mathcal{M}_2} = 7,850$ kg/m³, viscous

parameter $\eta = 0.1$ ms, bulk fracture energy release rate $\mathcal{G}_c^I = 0.01$ J/m² and $\mathcal{G}_c^{II} = 0.1$ J/m², interface fracture energy release rate $\mathcal{G}_c^I = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ J/m² and $\mathcal{G}_c^{II} = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$ J/m², critical gap ratio $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 5.0$ and the internal characteristic length scale $\ell_b = 0.1$ mm in bulk and $\ell_i = 0.02$ mm of interface. The prescribed vertical displacement is applied on the top-right node at the rate of $\dot{u}_y = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mm/s.

To investigate the failure mechanism, we look more closely into the spatio-temporal cohesive interface failure process and mechanical responses of the bi-material plate in this peeling test. Fig. 15(a) shows the spatio-temporal distribution of cohesive interface damage. We consider eight representative snapshots in Fig. 15(a) and denote them in the P-COD curve, as shown in Fig. 15(b). During the peeling test, we divide the cohesive interface failure process into two stages, i.e., interface fracture initiation (snapshots I ~ IV) and interface delamination (snapshots V ~ VIII). We observe that damage first initiates at the right end of interface, and the accumulation of damage results in the occurrence of interface fracture. During the interface fracture formation, the damage continues to concentrate around the interface fracture tip, which results in the creation of fracture process zone. Meanwhile, we find the slight

Fig. 13. Distributions of (a) phase field variable d , (b) normal gap δ_n , (c) degradation function $g_i(d)$ and (d) normal traction T_n along the middle line during cohesive interface failure onset.

Fig. 14. Schematics of the bi-material plate in the peeling test: (a) geometric and boundary conditions and (b) numerical discretization of bulk and interface finite elements.

strain-hardening phenomena at the stage of interface fracture initiation, which may be caused by the detached layer bridged two blocks. When the prescribed u_y continues to increase, the interface delamination with strain-softening phenomena happens.

To illustrate the numerical convergence of our simulations, we are concerned with three numerical specimens, where h_c is different and ℓ_b and ℓ_i is fixed. Numerical predictions of interface delamination and mechanical responses of three specimens are plotted in Fig. 16(a) and Fig. 16(b), respectively. The interface failure patterns in three bi-material specimens are close to each other, and the predicted P-COD curves of these specimens are also similar. These comparisons further indicate the numerical convergence and mesh independence of our new phase-field model for cohesive interface failure.

5.2. Example-II: Crack impinging on an interface

We further study the crack impinging on an interface using our model. We consider a square plate with 1.0 mm in length, which contains a pre-existing horizontal crack with the length of 0.5 mm at the mid-height, as shown in Fig. 17(a). Moreover, this square plate has an inclined interface. This interface is specified by the inclination angle $\beta = 30^\circ$ with respect to the horizontal direction. The prescribed vertical

displacements are applied on the bottom and top boundaries at the rate of $\dot{u}_y = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mm/s. In all numerical simulations, computational domain is composed of about 15,000 bulk finite elements and 200 interface finite elements, where $h_{\max} = 0.2$ mm and $h_{\min} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mm, as depicted in Fig. 17(b).

Referring to [21,94], we assume the following values of material parameters in numerical simulations: mass density $\rho = 2,450$ kg/m³, Young's modulus $E = 20.0$ MPa, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.37$, interface stiffness $k_n = 16.0$ MPa, viscous parameter $\eta = 0.1$ ms, critical gap ratio $\delta_1/\delta_0 = 3.0$, Mode-I bulk fracture energy release rate $G_c^I = 10.0$ J/m², Mode-II bulk fracture energy release rate $G_c^{II} = 150.0$ J/m², interface fracture energy release rate $G_c^I = 6.0$ J/m² in tensile and $G_c^{II} = 100.0$ J/m², and internal characteristic length scale $\ell_b = \ell_i = 0.01$ mm.

Figs. 18(a)–(c) show the spatio-temporal distribution of phase-field variable d , maximum shear stress τ_{\max} and the major principal stress σ_1 , respectively. We find that cracks initiated from the pre-existing crack tip first deflect along the inclined interface, then interface crack kinking out of the interface happens after interface crack deflection at the certain distance. Crack kinking out of the interface stems from the competing mechanism. From Figs. 17(b)–(c), we observe that maximum shear stress τ_{\max} drives the crack deflection/interface crack decohesion, while the major principal stress σ_1 drives the crack leaving the interface and propagating in a different direction.

Fig. 15. Cohesive interface failure process: (a) the spatio-temporal distribution of d and (b) mechanical response of a bi-material plate in the peeling test.

Fig. 16. Effect of h_e on the cohesive interface failure behaviors in numerical tests with the fixed ℓ_b and ℓ_i : (a) interface delamination patterns and (b) P-COD curves.

Fig. 17. Schematics of a square plate containing a horizontal crack and an inclined interface subjected to uniaxial tension: (a) geometry and boundary; (b) evolution of crack-interface interaction failure process.

Fig. 18. Spatio-temporal distribution during crack-interface interaction failure process: (a) phase-field variable, (b) maximum shear stress and (c) major principal stress.

To study the effect of critical gap ratio on the crack-interface interaction failure patterns, we simulate six samples with different δ_1/δ_0 under 2D plane strain assumption. The critical gap ratio δ_1/δ_0 varies from 1.0 to 6.0 with the increment of 1.0. Fig. 19 shows the resulting ultimate interface failure pattern, indicating that the critical gap ratio play an important role in crack impinging on interfaces. We observe the transformation from crack deflection along the interface to crack kinking out of the interface. When δ_1/δ_0 increases from 1.0 to 3.0, the length of crack deflection path decreases (Figs. 19 a–c), indicating crack kinking out of the interface becomes easy to happen. However, when δ_1/δ_0 increases from 3.0 to 6.0, crack deflection prevails (Figs. 19 c–f), suggesting the inhibition of crack kinking out of interfaces.

To investigate the effect of interface and bulk fracture energy release rates on the crack impinging failure, we model four numerical samples with different G_i/G_c . The ratio of G_i/G_c is changed from 1.0 to 0.4 in the decrement of 0.2. We depict the cohesive interface failure patterns of these samples in Fig. 20, which suggests that critical fracture energy release rates in bulk and interface regions significantly impact the crack deflection, kinking and penetration. When G_i/G_c decreases from 1.0 to 0.4, the ultimate failure pattern first changes from crack penetration (Fig. 20a) to crack kinking out of interfaces (Fig. 20 b–c), then to the crack deflection along interfaces (Fig. 20 d).

To further explore the effect of interface inclination angle β on the failure patterns in crack impinging problems, we consider five numerical samples with the preexisting interfaces. The inclination angle of preexisting interfaces are various, i.e., $\beta = 15^\circ$, $\beta = 30^\circ$, $\beta = 45^\circ$, $\beta = 60^\circ$ and $\beta = 75^\circ$. Fig. 21 presents the ultimate failure patterns of these samples, suggesting that β is a key factor dominating the cohesive interface failure patterns. We observe from Fig. 21 that the increase of β promotes the transition from crack deflection to crack penetration, which agrees with the theoretical trend [21]. At the lower β , crack deflection dominates the ultimate failure pattern (Figs. 21 a–b), whereas crack penetration controls the final failure pattern at the larger β (Figs. 21 d–e). When β is medium, i.e., $\beta = 45^\circ$, crack kinks out of the pre-existing interface, as shown in Fig. 21(c).

In the above numerical analysis, we summarize three different crack-interface interaction failure patterns in the crack impinging on

interfaces problem, including crack deflection (i.e., interface decohesion), crack kinking and crack penetration, as plotted in Fig. 22(a). For the specific $G_i/G_c = 0.6$, the crack-interface interaction failure patterns are classified into the space of β and δ_1/δ_0 (see Fig. 22b), suggesting the contribution of coupling β and δ_1/δ_0 to the ultimate failure modes. We observe that the large value of β dominates crack penetration, while crack kinking generally occurs when considering the low δ_1/δ_0 and small β . This classification provides a better understanding of the coupling effects of material properties and geometric parameters on the crack-interface interaction failure modes.

6. Conclusions

In this work, a new phase-field model for modeling cohesive interface failure in quasi-brittle solids is proposed. Our model has the following innovative features: (i) traction–separation–damage law on the zero-thickness interface elements; (ii) a new energetic degradation function bypassing tension-cut off in the classical CZM. These new features help to formulate new failure driving forces, which ensures the simulation of bulk fracture and cohesive interface failure within a unified phase-field framework. Moreover, we have employed a staggered numerical time-integration strategy with the explicit central-difference scheme for displacements and the forward-difference scheme for the phase-field variable. We have simulated a square plate with a horizontal interface under uniform tension in a plane strain case and a mode-I delamination test in a 3D case as two benchmark problems for numerical validation. Furthermore, our model is applied to study the peeling tests and crack impinging on interfaces. The effects of toughness ratio, critical gap ratio, and interface inclination angle on the crack-interface interaction failure characteristics are considered. Our proposed framework can be developed to study the anisotropic interface failure problems [85] and dissimilar layers/inclusions in geological media [95]. Furthermore, some multi-phase-field strategies for distinguishing different failure modes [53,77] can be incorporated into the proposed phase-field model for complex failure analysis in interface and bulk regions. Researches in these directions are underway.

Fig. 19. Effect of critical gap ratio δ_1/δ_0 on the crack-interface interaction failure patterns.

Fig. 20. Effect of toughness ratio in bulk and interface regions G_i/G_c on the crack-interface interaction failure patterns.

Fig. 21. Effect of interface inclination angle β on the crack-interface interaction failure patterns.

Fig. 22. Summary of crack-interface interaction failure patterns: (a) schematics of crack deflection, crack kinking and crack penetration; (b) classification in the space of β and δ_1/δ_0 for the quasi-brittle solids with the specific $G_i/G_c = 0.6$.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sijia Liu: Methodology, Software, Validation, Data analysis, Investigation. **Yunteng Wang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data analysis, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Review revision & editing. **Wei Wu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Review revision & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgments

Authors wish to acknowledge the support from National Key Research and Development Program of China (Grant No. 2022YFE0137200) and OeAD-GmbH Scientific & Technological Cooperation (WTZ) Austria/China program. The corresponding author acknowledges financial support from the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for Lise Meitner Programme (Grant No. M 3340-N) and Otto Pregl Foundation of Fundamental Geotechnical Research in Vienna. Furthermore, the second and third authors would like to thank the European Union Horizon 2020 RISE projects, HERCULES (Grant No. 778360) and FRAMED (Grant No. 734485).

References

- [1] Li H, Yu Y, Xu X, Chen T, Lu W. Enhancing the fracture toughness of laminated composites through carbon nanotube belt stitching. *Compos Sci Technol* 2021;204:108632.
- [2] Rao S, Budzik MK, Dias MA. On microscopic analysis of fracture in unidirectional composite material using phase field modelling. *Compos Sci Technol* 2022;220:109242.
- [3] Fan W, Yang H, Taylor AC. Numerical analysis of fracture in interpenetrating phase composites based on crack phase field model. *Compos Sci Technol* 2022;109873.
- [4] Berkowitz B. Characterizing flow and transport in fractured geological media: A review. *Adv Water Resour* 2002;25(8–12):861–84.
- [5] Ueda T, Dai J. Interface bond between FRP sheets and concrete substrates: properties numerical modeling and roles in member behaviour. *Progr Struct Eng Mater* 2005;7(1):27–43.
- [6] Tao R, Alfano M, Lubineau G. Laser-based surface patterning of composite plates for improved secondary adhesive bonding. *Composites A* 2018;109:84–94.
- [7] Daghia F, Fouquet V, Mabileau L. Improving the crack propagation response of layered and bonded structures through dissipation mechanisms at different length scales. *Int J Solids Struct* 2022;254:111910.
- [8] Wang L, Zhang X, Tinti S. Large deformation dynamic analysis of progressive failure in layered clayey slopes under seismic loading using the particle finite element method. *Acta Geotech* 2021;16(8):2435–48.
- [9] Wang J, Wang S, Su A, Xiang W, Xiong C, Blum P. Simulating landslide-induced tsunamis in the Yangtze River at the Three Gorges in China. *Acta Geotech* 2021;16(8):2487–503.
- [10] Rui S, Wang L, Guo Z, Cheng X, Wu B. Monotonic behavior of interface shear between carbonate sands and steel. *Acta Geotech* 2021;16(1):167–87.
- [11] Nguyen-Thanh N, Li W, Huang J, Zhou K. Multi phase-field modeling of anisotropic crack propagation in 3D fiber-reinforced composites based on an adaptive isogeometric meshfree collocation method. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;393:114794.
- [12] Zeng X, Wei Y. Crack deflection in brittle media with heterogeneous interfaces and its application in shale fracking. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2017;101:235–49.
- [13] Chen H, Zhang C, Lu Q, Chen H, Yang Z, Wen Y, Chen L, et al. A two-set order parameters phase-field modeling of crack deflection/penetration in a heterogeneous microstructure. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2019;347:1085–104.
- [14] Pitkethly MJ, Favre JP, Gaur U, Jakubowski J, Mudrich SF, Caldwell DL, Verpoest I, et al. A round-robin programme on interfacial test methods. *Compos Sci Technol* 1993;48(1–4):205–14.
- [15] Réquillé S, Le Duigou A, Bourmaud A, Baley C. Interfacial properties of hemp fiber/epoxy system measured by microdroplet test: Effect of relative humidity. *Compos Sci Technol* 2019;181:107694.
- [16] Williams M. The stresses around a fault or crack in dissimilar media. *Bull Seismol Soc Am* 1959;49(2):199–204.
- [17] Parmigiani JP, Thouless MD. The roles of toughness and cohesive strength on crack deflection at interfaces. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2006;54(2):266–87.
- [18] Cornetti P, Mantič V, Carpinteri A. Finite fracture mechanics at elastic interfaces. *Int J Solids Struct* 2012;49(7–8):1022–32.
- [19] Lee W, Yoo YH, Shin H. Reconsideration of crack deflection at planar interfaces in layered systems. *Compos Sci Technol* 2004;64(15):2415–23.
- [20] Parab ND, Chen WW. Crack propagation through interfaces in a borosilicate glass and a glass ceramic. *Int J Appl Glass Sci* 2014;5(4):353–62.
- [21] Paggi M, Reinoso J. Revisiting the problem of a crack impinging on an interface: a modeling framework for the interaction between the phase field approach for brittle fracture and the interface cohesive zone model. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2017;321:145–72.
- [22] Martin E, Leguillon D, Lacroix C. A revisited criterion for crack deflection at an interface in a brittle bimaterial. *Compos Sci Technol* 2001;61(12):1671–9.
- [23] Daniel R, Meindlhumer M, Baumegger W, Zalesak J, Sartory B, Burghammer M, Keckes J, et al. Grain boundary design of thin films: using tilted brittle interfaces for multiple crack deflection toughening. *Acta Mater* 2017;122:130–7.
- [24] Wang Y, Waisman H. Progressive delamination analysis of composite materials using XFEM and a discrete damage zone model. *Comput Mech* 2015;55(1):1–26.
- [25] Zhao L, Zhi J, Zhang J, Liu Z, Hu N. XFEM simulation of delamination in composite laminates. *Composites A* 2016;80:61–71.
- [26] Li G, Yin BB, Zhang LW, Liew KM. A framework for phase-field modeling of interfacial debonding and frictional slipping in heterogeneous composites. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2021;382:113872.
- [27] Pinho ST, Iannucci L, Robinson P. Physically based failure models and criteria for laminated fibre-reinforced composites with emphasis on fibre kinking part II: FE implementation. *Compos A Appl Sci Manuf* 2006;37(5):766–77.
- [28] Wisnom MR. Modelling discrete failures in composites with interface elements. *Composites A* 2010;41(7):795–805.
- [29] Paggi M, Reinoso J. An anisotropic large displacement cohesive zone model for fibrillar and crazing interfaces. *Int J Solids Struct* 2015;69:106–20.

- [30] Quintanas-Corominas A, Turon A, Reinoso J, Casoni E, Paggi M, Mayugo JA. A phase field approach enhanced with a cohesive zone model for modeling delamination induced by matrix cracking. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2020;358:112618.
- [31] Ghosh G, Duddu R, Annavarapu C. A stabilized finite element method for enforcing stiff anisotropic cohesive laws using interface elements. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2019;348:1013–38.
- [32] Lee S, Ji W. Measurement of pure mode I fracture toughness at a sandwich interface and parametrization of the R-curve for a cohesive element. *Compos Struct* 2022;291:115599.
- [33] Moës N, Dolbow J, Belytschko T. A finite element method for crack growth without remeshing. *Internat J Numer Methods Engrg* 1999;46(1):131–50.
- [34] Moës N, Belytschko T. Extended finite element method for cohesive crack growth. *Eng Fract Mech* 2002;69(7):813–33.
- [35] Higuchi R, Okabe T, Nagashima T. Numerical simulation of progressive damage and failure in composite laminates using XFEM/CZM coupled approach. *Composites A* 2017;95:197–207.
- [36] Wang C. Transverse crack evolution modeling of cross-ply laminates with a single layer of phantom node intraply elements for identically-oriented ply groups. *Compos Struct* 2020;254:112842.
- [37] Song JH, Wang H, Belytschko T. A comparative study on finite element methods for dynamic fracture. *Comput Mech* 2008;42(2):239–50.
- [38] Stein N, Dölling S, Chalkiadaki K, Becker W, Weißgraber P. Enhanced XFEM for crack deflection in multi-material joints. *Int J Fract* 2017;207(2):193–210.
- [39] Yin S, Zhang N, Liu P, Liu J, Yu T, Gu S, Cong Y. Dynamic fracture analysis of the linearly uncoupled and coupled physical phenomena by the variable-node multiscale XFEM. *Eng Fract Mech* 2021;254:107941.
- [40] Francfort GA, Marigo JJ. Revisiting brittle fracture as an energy minimization problem. *J Mech Phys Solids* 1998;46(8):1319–42.
- [41] Bourdin B, Francfort GA, Marigo JJ. Numerical experiments in revisited brittle fracture. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2000;48(4):797–826.
- [42] Silling SA. Reformulation of elasticity theory for discontinuities and long-range forces. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2000;48(1):175–209.
- [43] Wang Y, Zhou X, Xu X. Numerical simulation of propagation and coalescence of flaws in rock materials under compressive loads using the extended non-ordinary state-based peridynamics. *Eng Fract Mech* 2016;163:248–73.
- [44] Wang Y, Zhou X, Shou Y. The modeling of crack propagation and coalescence in rocks under uniaxial compression using the novel conjugated bond-based peridynamics. *Int J Mech Sci* 2017;128:614–43.
- [45] Wang Y, Zhou X, Wang Y, Shou Y. A 3-D conjugated bond-pair-based peridynamic formulation for initiation and propagation of cracks in brittle solids. *Int J Solids Struct* 2018;134:89–115.
- [46] Wang YT, Zhou XP, Kou MM. Three-dimensional numerical study on the failure characteristics of intermittent fissures under compressive-shear loads. *Acta Geotech* 2019;14:1161–93.
- [47] Zhou XP, Wang YT. State-of-the-art review on the progressive failure characteristics of geomaterials in peridynamic theory. *J Eng Mech* 2021;147(1):03120001. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EM.1943-7889.0001876](http://dx.doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EM.1943-7889.0001876).
- [48] Min L, Hu X, Yao W, Bui TQ, Zhang P. On realizing specific failure initiation criteria in the phase field model. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;394:114881.
- [49] Miehe C, Hofacker M, Welschinger F. A phase field model for rate-independent crack propagation: Robust algorithmic implementation based on operator splits. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2010;199(45–48):2765–78.
- [50] Amor H, Marigo JJ, Maurini C. Regularized formulation of the variational brittle fracture with unilateral contact: Numerical experiments. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2009;57(8):1209–29.
- [51] Liu S, Wang Y, Peng C, Wu W. A thermodynamically consistent phase field model for mixed-mode fracture in rock-like materials. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;392:114642.
- [52] Xu Y, Zhou S, Xia C, Hu Y. A new phase field model for mixed-mode brittle fractures in rocks modified from triple shear energy criterion. *Acta Geotech* 2022;17(12):5613–37.
- [53] Choo J, Sun Y, Fei F. Size effects on the strength and cracking behavior of flawed rocks under uniaxial compression: from laboratory scale to field scale. *Acta Geotech* 2023;1–18. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/S11440-023-01806-7>.
- [54] Ambati M, Gerasimov T, De Lorenzis L. Phase-field modeling of ductile fracture. *Comput Mech* 2015;55(5):1017–40.
- [55] Ambati M, Kruse R, De Lorenzis L. A phase-field model for ductile fracture at finite strains and its experimental verification. *Comput Mech* 2016;57(1):149–67.
- [56] Hofacker M, Miehe C. A phase field model of dynamic fracture: Robust field updates for the analysis of complex crack patterns. *Internat J Numer Methods Engrg* 2013;93(3):276–301.
- [57] Nguyen VP, Wu JY. Modeling dynamic fracture of solids with a phase-field regularized cohesive zone model. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2018;340:1000–22.
- [58] Chukwudozie C, Bourdin B, Yoshioka K. A variational phase-field model for hydraulic fracturing in porous media. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2019;347:957–82.
- [59] Zhou S, Zhuang X. Phase field modeling of hydraulic fracture propagation in transversely isotropic poroelastic media. *Acta Geotech* 2020;15(9):2599–618.
- [60] Ip SC, Borja RI. A phase-field approach for compaction band formation due to grain crushing. *Int J Numer Anal Methods Geomech* 2022;46(16):2965–87.
- [61] Wang Y, Borja RI, Wu W. Dynamic strain localization into a compaction band via a phase-field approach. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2023;173:105228.
- [62] Carollo V, Reinoso J, Paggi M. A 3D finite strain model for intralayer and interlayer crack simulation coupling the phase field approach and cohesive zone model. *Compos Struct* 2017;182:636–51.
- [63] Nguyen TT, Réthoré J, Yvonnet J, Baietto MC. Multi-phase-field modeling of anisotropic crack propagation for polycrystalline materials. *Comput Mech* 2017;60(2):289–314.
- [64] Guillén-Hernández T, García IG, Reinoso J, Paggi M. A micromechanical analysis of inter-fiber failure in long reinforced composites based on the phase field approach of fracture combined with the cohesive zone model. *Int J Fract* 2019;220(2):181–203.
- [65] Mandal TK, Nguyen VP, Wu JY. A length scale insensitive anisotropic phase field fracture model for hyperelastic composites. *Int J Mech Sci* 2020;188:105941.
- [66] Pranavi D, Rajagopal A, Reddy JN. Interaction of anisotropic crack phase field with interface cohesive zone model for fiber reinforced composites. *Compos Struct* 2021;270:114038.
- [67] Nguyen TT, Yvonnet J, Zhu QZ, Bornert M, Chateau C. A phase-field method for computational modeling of interfacial damage interacting with crack propagation in realistic microstructures obtained by microtomography. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2016;312:567–95.
- [68] Nguyen TT, Yvonnet J, Waldmann D, He QC. Phase field modeling of interfacial damage in heterogeneous media with stiff and soft interphases. *Eng Fract Mech* 2019;218:106574.
- [69] Hansen-Dörr AC, de Borst R, Hennig P, Kästner M. Phase-field modelling of interface failure in brittle materials. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2019;346:25–42.
- [70] Yoshioka K, Mollaali M, Kolditz O. Variational phase-field fracture modeling with interfaces. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2021;384:113951.
- [71] Li G, Yin BB, Zhang LW, Liew KM. Modeling microfracture evolution in heterogeneous composites: A coupled cohesive phase-field model. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2020;142:103968.
- [72] Schöller L, Schneider D, Herrmann C, Prahs A, Nestler B. Phase-field modeling of crack propagation in heterogeneous materials with multiple crack order parameters. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;395:114965.
- [73] Ma PS, Ye JY, Tian K, Chen XH, Zhang LW. Fracture phase field modeling of 3D stitched composite with optimized suture design. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;392:114650.
- [74] Verhoosel CV, de Borst R. A phase-field model for cohesive fracture. *Internat J Numer Methods Engrg* 2013;96(1):43–62.
- [75] Zhang P, Feng Y, Bui TQ, Hu X, Yao W. Modelling distinct failure mechanisms in composite materials by a combined phase field method. *Compos Struct* 2020;232:111551.
- [76] Zhang P, Hu X, Bui TQ, Yao W. Phase field modeling of fracture in fiber reinforced composite laminate. *Int J Mech Sci* 2019;161:105008.
- [77] Zhang P, Tan S, Hu X, Yao W, Zhuang X. A double-phase field model for multiple failures in composites. *Compos Struct* 2022;293:115730.
- [78] Paggi M, Corrado M, Reinoso J. Fracture of solar-grade anisotropic polycrystalline silicon: A combined phase field-cohesive zone model approach. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2018;330:123–48.
- [79] Tarafder P, Dan S, Ghosh S. Finite deformation cohesive zone phase field model for crack propagation in multi-phase microstructures. *Comput Mech* 2020;66(3):723–43.
- [80] Bui TQ, Hu X. A review of phase-field models fundamentals and their applications to composite laminates. *Eng Fract Mech* 2021;248:107705.
- [81] Chen L, de Borst R. Phase-field modelling of cohesive fracture. *Eur J Mech A Solids* 2021;90:104343.
- [82] Vignollet J, May S, De Borst R, Verhoosel CV. Phase-field models for brittle and cohesive fracture. *Meccanica* 2014;49(11):2587–601.
- [83] May S, Vignollet J, De Borst R. A numerical assessment of phase-field models for brittle and cohesive fracture: *Gamma* - convergence and stress oscillations. *Eur J Mech A Solids* 2015;52:72–84.
- [84] Feng DC, Wu JY. Phase-field regularized cohesive zone model (CZM) and size effect of concrete. *Eng Fract Mech* 2018;197:66–79.
- [85] Rezaei S, Harandi A, Brepolts T, Reese S. An anisotropic cohesive fracture model: Advantages and limitations of length-scale insensitive phase-field damage models. *Eng Fract Mech* 2022;261:108177.
- [86] Mandal TK, Nguyen VP, Wu JY. Length scale and mesh bias sensitivity of phase-field models for brittle and cohesive fracture. *Eng Fract Mech* 2019;217:106532.
- [87] Wu JY. A unified phase-field theory for the mechanics of damage and quasi-brittle failure. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2017;103:72–99.
- [88] Lorentz E, Godard V. Gradient damage models: Toward full-scale computations. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2011;200(21–22):1927–44.
- [89] Labanda NA, Espath L, Calo VM. A spatio-temporal adaptive phase-field fracture method. *Comput Methods Appl Mech Engrg* 2022;392:114675.
- [90] Sadaba S, Romero I, Gonzalez C, Llorca J. A stable X-FEM in cohesive transition from closed to open crack. *Internat J Numer Methods Engrg* 2015;101(7):540–70.

- [91] Huang D, Sheng B, Shen Y, Chui YH. An analytical solution for double cantilever beam based on elastic–plastic bilinear cohesive law: Analysis for mode I fracture of fibrous composites. *Eng Fract Mech* 2018;193:66–76.
- [92] Reinoso J, Paggi M. A consistent interface element formulation for geometrical and material nonlinearities. *Comput Mech* 2014;54(6):1569–81.
- [93] Kumar PKAV, Dean A, Sahraee S, Reinoso J, Paggi M. Non-linear thermoelastic analysis of thin-walled structures with cohesive-like interfaces relying on the solid shell concept. *Finite Elem Anal Des* 2022;202:103696.
- [94] Zambrano J, Toro S, Sánchez PJ, Duda FP, Méndez CG, Huespe AE. Interaction analysis between a propagating crack and an interface: Phase field and cohesive surface models. *Int J Plasticity* 2022;103341.
- [95] Yoshioka K, Mollaali M, Mishaan G, Makhnenko R, Parisio F. Impact of grain and interface fracture surface energies on fracture propagation in granite. In: 55th US Rock mechanics/geomechanics symposium. 2021.